

Impediments to Employment of High Skilled Immigrants in Sweden

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Immigration for a very long time has had an immense contribution to the growth and prosperity of a country's economy, society and politics. Despite the fact that established economies depend on foreign-trained labor, employment is one of immigrants' most basic needs in a new country. Immigrants have faced strains regardless of the fact that they arrive in a country with higher education levels than local citizens (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014).

This study investigates the experiences of highly educated immigrants in the labor markets in foreign countries, the challenges to acquiring employment opportunities with Sweden as the case study. When conducting this study, several successful employment benchmarks were approached. Among the challenges highly educated Swedish immigrants have faced in securing employment include government policies barring immigrants from securing employment opportunities, language incompetence owed to the language barrier, non-recognition of overseas credentials, lack of Swedish workplace experience and the mismatch of skills and job requirements (Joona, Gupta & Wadensjö 2014). Lundborg (2013) argues that the difficulty in securing employment among highly skilled Swedish immigrants is a globally faced phenomenon aggravated by the fact that they are not able to gain experience in new countries. This has resulted in the high unemployment rates and poverty among immigrants since it takes them a long time to get space in the country's labor markets. This prevents foreign-educated immigrant experts from positively contributing to the progress of the host country and many end up in low-paying jobs.

Background of the study

Immigrants with Swedish schooling, familiarity and past Swedish labor market experience have been noted to have a competitive advantage over others in the recruitment

procedures. Swedish immigrants are healthy, well-educated employment tourists whose resources and skills can be utilized to the advantage of the Swedish economy. Inability to secure employment among highly educated immigrants results in the waste of brains and waste of human potential due to lack of immigrant integration into the Swedish labor market.

Discrimination, autocratic practices, ignorance and social injustices are among the factors that incite lack of immigrant integration into the Swedish job market (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014).

Most immigrants who secure employment opportunities in Sweden are denied space in job market upper echelons due to lack of Swedish labor experience. Due to this, immigrants end up taking low paying jobs that do not require experience since these are the ones that natives consider invaluable as is the case with some immigrants who end up working as servants and garden attendants since these do not require experience in the Swedish context. Emilsson, Magnusson, Osanami, Torgren and Bevelander (2014) argue that immigrants who go back to school to acquire tertiary education and educational levels of the local population still do not secure more employment opportunities in comparison with locals. It is therefore imperative to initiate studies to shed light on this subject and find solutions with the aim of remediating the unequal employment opportunities for highly qualified immigrants in comparison with the locals.

Immigrants' Contribution to the Swedish Economy and Challenges They Face

There is a wide spread notion among the locals in Sweden that immigrants are weakening the economy by getting free taxpayer money, taking their jobs, wasting national resources among other issues. The debate on whether immigrants are benefiting or sabotaging the country has come up on different academic and even political platforms (Hocking & Spence 2016). The harsh reality is that immigrants face more problems in Sweden than at home despite their high hopes. The fact that immigrants and refugees flee their countries search for employment and

peace is a sufficient reason to believe that they are seeking to develop a new society. Zheng and Ejeremo et al (2015) contend that foreign job seekers and refugees exploit the economy since they receive government services that they are neither taxed nor paying for as some believe that immigrants do not in any way contribute to the economy. Contrarily, immigrants have contributed to the Swedish economy in different ways for years in many ways including improving investments and consumption of local products and services apart from filling many employment positions leading to subsidiary responsibility formation, increased productivity and lower cost of goods (Dadush 2014). In the construction industry, immigrants have contributed and helped in building as they provide low cost labor leading to lower item prices as well as higher profits to the local employers (Kvedaraite, Baksys, Repeckiene & Glinskiene 2015). They are also a crucial consumer base since the biggest parts of their wages are consumed locally.

The notion that immigrants exploit the Swedish economy is unfounded since immigrants contribute to wealth creation and economic activities and without this significantly contribution, the Swedish economy would improve at a very slow rate since most Swedish immigrants are highly educated young and efficient people who help build the economy apart from paying taxes through sales tax and pay income tax and therefore contributing to education, healthcare and other services either directly or indirectly (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014). They, in addition, fill manual labor positions despised by the locals amid arguments by anti-immigrants that they contribute less that cannot commensurate the services they receive from the Swedish government. The anti-immigrant calls also argue that immigrants provide cheap labor hence bringing down the cost of labor and affecting the locals and are therefore a recipe to the fall of the Swedish economy (Joon, Gupta & Wadensjo 2014).

Immigrants face high marginalization and discrimination rates in addition to their economic challenges which are not a commonplace to the local populations. They are not given equal employment opportunities to advance and progress despite being highly qualified. It has been established that admission of highly skilled immigrant labor increases and expands employment opportunities for local skilled labor as they enhance organizational innovation levels (Forsgren 2015). Swedish workplace inexperience has been unfairly treated as lack of knowledge of the Swedish work customs and cultures as a basis of locking immigrants out of employment opportunities. It has also been established that recruitment processes in Sweden apply prejudicial treatments to immigrants (Ghimire & Mahajarn 2015).

Immigrants face a lot of employment challenges in the Swedish labor market and awareness creation is necessary to ensure that highly skilled immigrant job seekers are accorded fairer treatment as the locals to meaningfully contribute to the growth of the economy. Future research needs to approach strategies to minimize the impacts of existing job market barriers on high skilled immigrant population.

Problem statement

A number of researches have shed light on income inequality between the local populace and immigrants in several nations with the same characteristics as Sweden. Their findings give theoretical explanations to barriers to immigrant employment and assimilation into the local job market. There has also been less focus on the impediments to immigrant employment. This study takes a look into the pertinent elements for the employment of highly foreign-trained jobseekers into the Swedish job market. In light of these challenges foreign jobseekers face in Sweden, this study aims to raise awareness on the predicaments of highly-skilled immigrants and the contribution they can make in the Swedish economy and society. The complexity of the current

workplace in Sweden and globally represents the challenges organizations face. High-skilled human capital is underutilized and research into the subject can help remediate the problem by exploring the reasons behind the poor performance of expatriate and immigrant workers in Sweden.

Immigrants do not represent competition in the labor market as perceived by the Swedish locals as immigrant workers have been proven to increase productivity, income and opportunities in Sweden (Jaumotte, Koloskova & Saxena 2016). Neighborly kindness and inventiveness should be embraced by critics of immigrant employment in order to contribute to making Sweden a land of opportunities and productive dreams to all. Sweden's current financial crisis has pushed its government to liberalizing the labor third-world migration policy after many years of limiting systems and has since opened its labor market to the world resulting in the expansion of the labor market.

Study Objectives

The main objective of the study is investigates the impediments to highly-skilled immigrant labor employment in Sweden.

Specific study objectives are:

1. Identifying crucial factors to the employment of high-skilled immigrant workers
2. Critically exploring recruitment complications to high-skilled immigrant jobseekers
3. Critically investigating the main obstacles to high-skilled immigrant recruitment in Sweden
4. Examining barriers to access to employment opportunities among immigrants in Sweden

Main research question

The main research question is to establish the impediments or challenges to the employment of high-skilled immigrant workforce?

Sub research questions

1. What are the crucial factors for the recruitment of high-skilled immigrant workers and expatriates?
2. Do immigrants encounter complications when accessing jobs in Sweden?
3. What are the obstacles to the immigrant recruitment process in Sweden?
4. What other barriers do high-skilled immigrants face when trying to access job opportunities in Sweden?

Significance of the study

There are profound concerns on the employment of immigrants and the importance of education in foreign nations in recruitment processes. This study is valuable to the government of Sweden, qualified foreign nationals seeking employment opportunities and other people in similar situations not only in Sweden but globally. This study is also important to the Swedish job market as it raises awareness by shedding light on the existence of obstacles to the employment of high-skilled immigrant labor force that's underutilized. The Swedish directorate of immigration will also find this study useful as it seeks answers to the declining high-skilled immigrant and expatriate workforce in the country (Czaika & Parsons 2017).

Limitations of the Research

The research focused on immigrant employment impediments in Sweden and did not look at the socio-economic challenges that immigrants face. The scope of the study is narrow and has certain delimitations such as the lack of will among participants to take part in the study due to its

sensitivity, lack of the overall Swedish employment picture due to small study sample and the inaccuracy of the answers offered by participants thereby affecting the findings' reliability.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter evaluates a number of studies on the skilled immigrant employment impediments in Sweden in relation to the labor market forces and contribution to the national economy. To provide a rigorous and extensive rationale for conducting the study, a comprehensive review was done setting the context of the study by offering an updated Swedish immigrant picture (Bandick, Gorg & Karpaty 2014). It also approaches the impediments that highly skilled immigrants face when seeking employment matching their skills.

The study's main focus is the immigrants' lack of experience and Swedish job market requirements. In light of this problem, the study presents recommendations by various authors and researchers on the best strategy to tackle employment impediments job market in Sweden. This chapter also takes a look into theories that illuminate cultural differences in the employment market and inspires future research on the subject.

Sweden receives immigrants from different cultures and this has shaped the Swedish identity. Immigrants have become part of Sweden's political, financial and social fabric of Sweden over the past years with over 19% of the country's population being foreign; born in Europe. Together with immigrants from other diverse regions, Sweden houses immigrants that add up to nearly fifty percent of her population that contribute to approximately 60% of her job market growth (Joonas, Gupta & Wadensjo 2014). Over three-quarters of Sweden's immigrant population are visible minorities. Immigrants immensely contribute expertise and experience to the country's economy as they hold high educational qualifications as evidenced by the outcomes of the recent census which showed that 63% of Swedish immigrant population held university degrees and diplomas as compared with 33% of native Swedish citizens (Habti, Koikkalainen 2014).

It is imperative that immigrants are integrated into a country's economy for positive social development contribution. This chapter and critically analyzes the effectual immigrant entry and comprehensive integration into the labor market. Immigrant presence and contribution into a country's economy is increasingly becoming important despite unfavorable integration data results in the past years. Immigrants have been subjected to high poverty levels, unemployment, social segregation and poor working conditions in both short and long terms. Joblessness among immigrants in the nation was at 11% in 2010 with the employed ones earning an average annual salary of \$ 20, 000 in comparison to native Swedes' 3.8% unemployment rate and average earnings of \$62,000 (Habti, Koikkalainen 2014). This has, however, been blamed on economic situations, lack of appreciation for immigrants and failure of redistributive frameworks as the labor unions in the country (Joona, Gupta & Wadensjo 2014).

Theoretical frameworks

Two theories have been fronted to boost the understanding of immigrant population experiences in the Swedish labor market, namely, the shelter theory and the labor market segmentation and human capital theory. The labor market segmentation and human capital theory is important in understanding the Swedish context since it is the point system that is the foundation for immigrant selection. The point system is founded on the fact that there are certain immigrants suiting Swedish financial demands. This theory insinuates that skills and knowledge gained during a lifetime by way of experiences and education correlate with productive capacity. Wrench, Rea and Quali et al (2016) argues that this theory is not cogent in the Swedish context as professional Swedish immigrants are underutilized along with their human capital abilities despite the fact that they possess similar and even superior human resource skills to the native Swedes.

Labor market segmentation (split labor market) theory provides a supporting explanation for immigrant underemployment and inequality as it contends that job markets are grouped into primary and secondary impenetrable segments. The primary job market sector offers employees with a favorable working environment, job tenure and advancement opportunities while the secondary segment does not offer the favorable conditions of work and low compensation levels. This theory is important in that it helps in the understanding of the financial discriminations that immigrants undergo in a country's secondary labor market segment. It also identifies the ethical apathy resulting in the labor markets along ethnic lines (Labrianidis & Sykas 2015). A labor market must be split into two groups with varying labor prices or similar jobs. The theory also asserts that lack of immigrant work experience appreciation results in a Sweden-born worker-favoring economic system over foreign employees.

On the other hand, the labor market shelter theory contends that redistributive frameworks such as professional affiliations and labor union's creation and regulation of labor market shelters into primary markets force immigrants into the secondary labor markets. Social closure frameworks limit access to fair labor markets on the basis of ascribed traits since they are entrenched obstacles (Czaika & Parsons 2017). Failure to recognize foreign credentials is a way of denying immigrants access to work as a move to preserve particular key positions to Swedish-born applicants.

Labor market theories extensively explain the professional displacement and underemployment realities that a great number of professional immigrants experience in the Swedish job market. Mosneaga and Winther et al (2013) argues that these theories fail to explain why some professional immigrants with undesirable traits manage to secure employment opportunities in Sweden's job markets.

Immigrant Employment impediments

A study outlines such leading factors that affect outcomes of immigrant recruitment processes as failure to misrecognition of foreign credentials, language barrier and lack or limited experience on the Swedish work demands. Literature review of publications, reports and articles of the last decade, on the other hand, reveal issues on high skilled worker integration into the Swedish job market (Hedberg, Hermelin & Wsetermark 2014). The review correspondingly sought answers to several questions such as whether skilled immigrants should speak the Swedish local language to secure employment in the country's job industry, whether immigrants should have previous Swedish work experience in order to secure jobs, whether high skilled immigrants should retrain in Swedish universities and colleges find a place in the country's labor market and whether other obstacles exist that block high skilled immigrants from looking for and securing jobs in the Swedish labor market.

Non-recognition of foreign credentials

Sweden does not offer accreditation to foreign credentials and this has become one of the biggest impediments to securing professional employment opportunities. Professionals educated in foreign countries face Swedish professional regulations and undergo accreditation processes that systematically evaluate pre-migration credentials conducted by accrediting formations. Part from showcasing their language competence, immigrants are expected to demonstrate their educational expanse perceived as academic equivalency (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014). High skilled immigrants are also required to sit certification examinations as a qualification acknowledgement after pursuing appropriate experience in their respective nations. Swedish equivalency accreditation establishment processes are attainable in short time but complex and marred with uncoordinated and complicated institutional communications. Unfair and

discriminatory practices aggravate these situations and are also detrimental to immigrants' capacity to put their professional crafts into practice in the country.

Sweden lacks oversee credential recognizing, expert accreditation and licensing organization or body, a factor contributed to by the power separations between the federal and state government levels making the accreditation process unattainable. Federal prerogative in Sweden control immigration but upon settling in a province, an immigrant becomes subject to state law and subjected to professional and academic criteria that vary from province to province (Czaika & Parsons 2017). This is a subject to unfairness as it limits an immigrant's professional ability. Another limiting factor is the fact that Swedish professional bodies are only creditors with limited information on oversee learning systems and job experience equivalencies leading to denunciation of immigrant education since the whole process is tedious requiring a lot of significant financial resources without assurance of justice. Due to these factors, high skilled immigrants resort to low skilled job markets to fend for themselves and their families as they await accreditation while some do not pursue these pre-migration occupation processes.

Swedish workplace inexperience

Joona, Gupta & Wadensjo (2014) define Swedish workplace experience refers to the experience gained in a current or past Swedish employment construct that fits into the Swedish workplace culture, standards and skills. Such soft skills as business ethics and customs knowledge, teamwork, devoid to foreign accent and acculturation are also considered. Lack of Swedish workplace experience is made worse by prejudice, discrimination and social network absence. Another impediment to immigrant high skill employment is the lack of or insufficient appreciation by Swedish employers and regulatory bodies for foreign-county-gained work experience despite the remarkable work history possessed by high-skilled immigrant workforce

(Czaika & Parsons 2017). The same benchmarks that are a requirement to gaining entry into Sweden are inadequate for one to obtain appropriate work skills. Swedish employers fail to recognize prospective high skilled immigrants since they are unable to assess their foreign experience in the Swedish workplaces and this has been used by biased Swedish employers to deny immigrants work opportunities. Consequently, a great number of Swedish employers consider educational credentials from such areas as Africa, South Asia and Latin America as inferior, dissimilar and substandard to those acquired in North America and Europe. This implies that global professional bodies and learning institutions do not recognize educational credential from South Asia, Latin America and Africa in law, teaching and architecture with the toughest barrier being to foreign trained doctors.

A study by Joona, Gupta and Wadensjo (2014) shows that high skilled immigrants face painful struggle when seeking credential acknowledgement. According to this study, Sweden between 2000 and 2001 received over 124,700 high skilled immigrants. It was established that only 14% got their credential evaluated and accepted after six month stay in the country. Viberg and Gronlund et al (2013) reported in his labor policy changes study that Swedish employers from different organizations, firms and sectors found it difficult to assess high skilled immigrants but would not hire before comparing these qualifications to local standards. Most managers in Sweden contend that it is difficult to authenticate work experiences and references. In addition, Sweden's non-regulated vocations are immigrant unreceptive since Swedish experiences job postings prerequisites are proxy to enable employers understand the Swedish workplace including values, communication skills, operations, principles and crucial leadership skills. Many Swedish employers do not have an understanding of Swedish workplace business expectations and practices while believing that immigrants face a reverse burden in understanding and

acclimatizing the Swedish business culture. Swedish work experience as an employment factor has therefore been used to screen out high skilled immigrant job application together with cultural differences related to workplace norms and practices. These aspects are key to determining foreigners' Swedish workplace experience acquisition (Hatzigeorgiou & Lofefalk 2015).

In Sweden, workplace cultures include such practices as employers valuing leaders that give them the freedom to make decisions and determine suitable ways to undertake their roles. Swedish managers are also known for preferring workers that require minimal oversight and supervision when accomplishing set tasks. Sardan, Zhu and Veen et al (2016) posit that managers in this region prefer giving instructions and guidelines and employees too like being given detailed guidelines. Bevelander and Irastova (2014) assert that Swedish employers that employ immigrants from the region may find themselves trading incompetency blames with employees since they have different expectation from each other in efficient work inabilities (Kelly 2014). This means that Swedish managers tend to avoid employing foreigners to avoid such cases of inefficiency resulting in high skilled foreigners missing employment opportunities.

Cultural differences and culture shock additionally play crucial roles in recruitment process and affect the Swedish workplace cultural experiences. Such instances as speaking positively or highly of one's self are unacceptable and reprehensible in the Swedish culture as opposed to such cultures as the American case that treats it as 'selling one's self' as a job-seeking requirement. Avoiding direct eye contact during interviews is also considered lack of self-confidence and dishonesty in the Swedish culture but regarded as respect indicator in most immigrant cultures and universally. This has affected even high skilled immigrants from Arabic cultures where eye contact maintenance is regarded as a disrespect sign. These cultural

differences cost skilled immigrants job opportunities as they are disadvantaged in effective job seeking competition due to this lack of local experience.

A research by Mihi-Ramirez, Rogriguez and Metelski (2015) approached several acculturation challenges that skilled immigrants face with focus on immigrant's local experiences establishing that foreigners can be fully integrated and absorbed into local community if they acquire local accents and conducts. The research finds out that Swedes are more direct and immigrants must therefore try and accomplish tasks in this way as opposed to conducts in their native cultures. Nebilar, Venturi and Martin's (2013) study on reasons behind skilled laborers' struggles in foreign markets also found confirming results. The study asserts that particular cultures highly regard teamwork as Odlin et al (2013) contradict this by contending that Swedish cultures are individualistic since they are capitalistic and therefore may not value teamwork highly. The study also posits that Indian high skilled Swedish immigrant laborers tend not to interact in workplaces due to the caste systems back home and efforts contrary to this lead to wrangles and conflicts internally. In a study carried out by Odlin (2013), Latin American immigrants several cultural differences as they seek jobs as they felt left out due to the fact that they could not fit into the Swedish culture because they were unaccustomed and failed to recognize informal workplace interactions. 56% of respondents identified lack of Swedish experience as a personal and professional welfare impediment. Such local Swedish jokes, sport talks and news at workplaces and recruitment sites make immigrants feel like outsiders. Lack of local experience and preferences are pertinent workplace cultures that make high skilled immigrants in Sweden perform ineffectively.

The financial crisis in Sweden has pushed the Swedish government to liberalize migration labor policy for immigrants from their world countries after decades of limiting

systems and has adopted a worldwide open system that has resulted in an increased labor migration (Castles 2013). Swedish labor immigrants are categorized into three groups, namely, berry picking social employees, skilled employment seekers and low skilled immigrant job seekers. Demand driven organizations in Sweden use a model explainable through worker transitional networks access. This policy separates, analyzes and explains deferent labor migration types as they are diverse driving forces products (Congiano 2014). The policy reforms have been termed for years as vital transformation within the Swedish immigration labor market. A need to reform the Swedish immigration policy to enable Sweden meet future market place challenges is eminent by mitigating labor shortages in certain areas and occupations (Castles, De Haas & Miller 2013).

Language Barrier

High skilled immigrant job seekers might lack excellent communication skills, an impeding factor to securing jobs. Lack of communication expertise is perceived as the inability to communicate thereby limiting social performance and jobs and leading to loss of self-confidence, depression and withdrawal. In Osanami, Torngren and Holbrow's (2017) study on precarious migrant status and employment, academic qualification and lingual literacy were found to substantially affect immigrant's earnings. Another Simon, Ramos and Sanroma's (2014) study posits that lack of proper communication skills impedes high skill employment in Sweden. Companies seeking employees to handle its customers are not keen on recruiting employing graduates with linguistic inabilities even if they are native Swedes. Another study by Sylven (2014) contends that lack of linguistic skills among high skilled immigrant workers can impede their employment chances in technical jobs that require jargon explanation to customers and non-technical staff.

A study by Smith, Hadfield and Dunne et al (2016) found that foreign accents are not indicators of limited language abilities among high skilled immigrant professionals as they are educated on language competencies and there do not affect their assimilation into the Swedish labor market. Accents are insignificant to high skill immigrant employment. The type of accent may or may not favor an individual as immigrants with English accents are highly regarded in Sweden as compared to such English accents as Arabic and African ones. Successful job searches in Sweden differ from one immigrant to another with regards to accents. Another study by Sylven (2013) established that Swedish immigrants that have thick accents worked longer and harder to secure employment opportunities. Such immigrants are forced to seek language instructor's help in the job search process. The implication drawn here is that accents accentuate employer-interviewee linguistic differences. Van Ostaïjen, Reeger and Zelano et al (2017) assert that accents determine the type of treatment immigrants receive in relation to work skills.

Accents have a crucial role to play and pose considerable ramifications in the Swedish labor market for high skilled immigrant workers as they are not able to acquire work and experience.

Other impediments to professional immigrant employment in Sweden

Other forms of impediments to high skilled employment of immigrants include racism and xenophobia; pertinent issues in Sweden. Their prevalence is significant despite the fact that they are restrained. A study by somebody on immigrant socioeconomic detriments in the Swedish job markets assert that high skilled immigrants are accorded low professional status and salaries in comparison with locals. It outlines that Swedish immigrants are culturally faced with financial problems and economic disadvantages owing to their cultures, identities and religious affiliations. Affirmative findings from Takenoshita's (2010) research on immigrant

employment in Sweden contend that many Swedish immigrants faced skin color-based discrimination and as opposed to professional or educational acumen. The study also found out that white immigrants in Sweden faced insignificant disparities in earnings and compared to the large income disparities among minority immigrants. Professional immigrant workers that adapt to the difficult and unfavorable working conditions and environments receive meager compensations.

Chapter summery

The literature review selected and summarized crucial theoretical knowledge on impediments to high skilled immigrant employment and job market assimilations in Sweden. It also reviewed studies that assert that immigrant populations in Sweden are better educated but have limited work experience in the Swedish standards as compared to the locals. Regardless of their education standards of levels of experience that can benefit the country, Swedish immigrants experience difficulties in trying to secure jobs, which this is mainly due to factors such as lack of linguistic proficiency, Swedish workplace inexperience, discrimination, and non-recognition of international educational credentials.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The reliability, consistency, acceptability and reliability of a study are dependent on methodology and strategies employed while conducting it. This chapter entails Methodology standards for the design, approaches and ethical concerns of the study.

Design of the study

A qualitative approach that include tape-recording and interviews were employed to address the questions of the research informed by three reasons. The first reason is the subjective and detailed analysis of experiences and perspectives of the subjects on the study problem. Another reason is the flexibility to investigate the answers offered by the subjects for details setting precedents for asking questions such as ‘how’ and ‘why’. The third reason for using the qualitative approach is that it helped in data extraction where numerical data and sources could not be effective.

The study also employed a framework of the ground theory to generate new concepts and ideas as soon as they arose from the observations and data analysis in the course of the study. This approach allowed the openness with tractability in order to change the focus. Face-to face interviews with immigrants were carried out to mitigate in case of scanty research (Bevelander 2014). This is because immigrants were the best population to depict and explore explicitly their experiences. The evidence gathered by this study can be useful to institutions that seek to enrich public knowledge on high skilled immigrant market assimilation.

Sampling

The interest of the study was on skilled immigrants speaking other languages and seeking employment in Sweden with intent to generate new knowledge. The study intended to explore peculiarities in both national and cultural perspectives that hinder immigrant job search in the Swedish labor market. The study employed ‘purposive sampling’ technique and therefore only

subjects that met the criterion of selection participated in the study. This allowed the choosing of participants whose contribution was relevant to the study problem. Immigrants with less than seven year stay in Sweden were recruited to bring out the trends and emerging issues in immigrant settlement and job integration. Through this, fresh and accurate information was obtained that were not affected by time passage.

The subjects were expatriation applicants to Sweden and assisted the testing the labor market segmentation and human capital theory applicability (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014). The theories were important to the study due to the fact that the applicants were admitted to Sweden through the point system in appraising their educational credentials, work experiences and linguistic abilities according to the Swedish migration assessment levels. Immigrants from the former Soviet Union were selected since they represent the majority immigrant population in Sweden.

The 130 applicants' age range was between 20 and 60 years with 71 males and 59 females from Kalmar, Smaland contacted through e-mails and invitation letters. Coercive tactics were avoided during the research; instead, encouragement was employed for voluntary participation in the study. 120 people agreed to participate in the study and written agreements were presented for interviews and tape recording. The interviews were conducted at mutually appropriate places and time.

Employment backgrounds of the immigrants

The interviewed immigrants had at most seven year stay in Sweden. This was done to improve the research validity and relevance in capturing merging issues and current trends in immigrant employment. The interviewed immigrants were from different nationalities including the majority former Soviet Union nationals. They were also selected from different categories to establish their employability. Both employed and unemployed immigrants from different

employment backgrounds were incorporated. Also incorporated were high-skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled immigrant workers for comparison purposes. The high skilled immigrant respondents comprised of well-educated university degree holders and above. Some were medical doctors, bankers, lawyers, engineers and marketers who were the majority respondents. The semi-skilled respondents had a college diploma, certificate and technical skill holders from diverse industries. The unskilled immigrants lacked higher education and technical skills. This move to include all employability backgrounds ensured that all categories were included in the study so that it had a broader perspective in looking at the predicaments of the high-skilled immigrants from the comparisons.

Methods of data collection

In-depth Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data and capture every immigrant's story. A follow up on initial responses was done for clarification where necessary and further explicit disclosure of personal encounters (Bevelander & Spang 2014). Note-taking was also used during interviews in capturing non-verbal expressions and recoding crucial points made by the participant (Hood & Birkinshaw 2016). General personal information such as country of birth, Sweden stay duration and linguistic proficiency were requested at the start of the interviews. The participants were also asked to disclose the methods and techniques they used when searching for jobs, the challenges they faced and their personal opinions about job search processes. They were also asked about their Swedish workplace experiences; their understanding, relevance and their efforts to acquire it. The responses were fluent Swedish and English speakers allowing for English interviewing.

The interviews lasted for around 30-45 minutes and conducted between March and April 2017. The interviewing process development was in accordance with the literature review and immigrants' observation.

Sample Interview Questions Form

Date

Interview Questions on Impediments to Employment for High-Skilled Swedish Immigrants

Part I: General Information

- Q1. Kindly tell us about your country of birth. What was your occupation then?
- Q2. How old are you?
- Q3. What is your marital status?
- Q4. If married, does your spouse possess Swedish nationality?
- Q5. How long have you been staying in Sweden?

Part II: Education and Socio-Demography

- Q1. Which languages are you proficient in?
- Q2. Can you read and write in these languages?
- Q3. What is the highest level of studies that you have completed?
- Q4. What was your highest education level before migrating to Sweden?
- Q5. Do you possess a certificate or degree to demonstrate this level of studies?

Part III: Employment

- Q1. What is your occupation currently?
- Q2. Which tactics and techniques did you use during the job application process?
- Q3. Would you briefly outline some of the challenges or obstacles you faced during the job application process.
- Q4. What is your outlook/opinion about the entire job search process?

Part IV: Swedish Experience

- Q1. How would you describe your Swedish experience?

Q2: When did you hear it first?

Q3: How do you understand the concept of Swedish experience?

Q4. Does it have any relevance on your present circumstances or how you have worked to attain it?

Analysis of data

Qualitative data were analyzed via axial coding and open coding forms with the open coding form used during the primary interview transcript review. The larger data volumes were managed by condensing and categorizing using initial codes and themes. During the second phase of data analysis, axial coding was used with themes, coding and ideas arranged systematically in accordance with the critical axial theories for analysis and merging closely related models (Beine, Boucher, Burgoon, Crock, Gest, Hiscox & Thielemann 2016). Through this, four major categories surfaced during axial coding including dialect, employment gaining tactics, Swedish workplace experience and qualifications. In order to organize data into indicated sequence, groups and subgroup diagramming and regular evaluations were utilized. Analytic memos were also used to supplement the coding process.

Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations are among the most vital elements that guided the study since they are like laws and regulations governing a country. Researchers should always observe Confidentiality and privacy. Such ethical issues such as privacy, risk assessment, interview systems, confidentiality, written consent, research procedures and methods were explored and safeguarded in the preparation stages of this study (Beine, Boucher, Burgoon, Crock, Gest, Hiscox & Thielemann 2016). Interviewees were allowed to skip questions or forfeit the interview whenever they felt like avoiding answering unpleasant questions or uncertain. Emails were sent to 120 subjects to seek their participation in the research project and aliases were used

in place of names to guarantee privacy and confidentiality. The participants were assured that the study outcomes would be available to them after its completion (Bandick, Gorg & Karpaty 2014). This was done as a sign of goodwill to reassure them that they were respectfully and courteously regarded. They were also assured of identity secrecy and any effort to lay bare their personal information would be avoided. In the research documentation, subject and their professions, workstations and job descriptions were not revealed. The data gathered during the study was stored in a password secured laptop to avoid unauthorized access to participant's information.

The ethical consideration assurances made to participants ensured that the study achieved high credits that made the respondents feel free to use words and would not be used against them. This helped achieve trust of the participants at the initial stages of the study methodologies by creating good rapport. Through this, the study obtained sensitive data that would otherwise have been missed out.

Reliability and validity

These help researchers examine research finding believability and integrity by focusing on truthfulness, stability, consistency and precision of the requirements of the research. Steps were taken to ensure that similar outcomes would be realized in future studies in efforts to ensure reliability and high validity levels of this study. Face and content validity used ensured that aspects and questions were accurately depicted in the research.

Limitations of the study

The study's main limitation was the use of 120 participants since it was a small sample and therefore might not represent the views of the whole immigrant population. The interviews were also conducted on a small population section and might also pose unseen limitations. More significant results would have been realized if the research approached a broad cross-section sample. The failure of some participants to offer reliable outcomes also affected the study results.

Chapter Summary

This research relied on qualitative research design-interviews in research question answering.

This chapter provides an overview of the whole research procedure hence making easy the understanding of the research and its findings. Reliability and validity of the research tool and collected information will be cross-checked and ascertained as true through probing during the interviews and cross-checking the answered questionnaires. Analysis would be done through content/theme analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter delves into the findings from the personal interviews. The findings were organized according to research questions to make easy understanding.

Educational Backgrounds

Information on educational qualifications was sought to explore participants' capabilities and skills. 16% of the participants had degrees from Swedish institutions. Majority of the participants were educated outside Sweden and the rest had degrees from both Swedish and foreign institutions. The use of four-item Likert scale outlined that 75 participants reported that Swedish educational backgrounds had a crucial role in obtaining employment (Kelly, 2015). 45 of the participants held a different opinion with the rest on the role of Swedish degree in securing employment in the country.

A person's education is an asset in connection with the job market meaning that outsiders are always considered to have little education by recruiters in the host nation. This confirms that immigrants holding Swedish degrees have higher chances in securing employment. A small number of participants asserted that immigrants without Swedish degrees had higher chances of securing employment in Sweden. One of the participants who was a medical doctor claimed that he has never secured a permanent employment in the country due to his immigrant status despite having stayed in the country for the four years. He argued that the process of securing a license takes more than four years besides being very hectic

Immigrants' former work experience

All of the respondents in the study offered data on their previous job involvements inside and outside Sweden. 60% of the respondents were established to have previous work experiences. 82% majority respondents reported that they had previous work experiences in various countries and not in Sweden. The literature review revealed that immigrants must have

Swedish work experiences work in Sweden. It was found therefore found that past Swedish skills were crucial in finding employment, except for immigrants from nations in Europe and North America. 20% of respondents contradicted the articulation that Swedish experience was effective for finding work among immigrants in the Swedish labor market. 26.7% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the scale item while majority 54.3% believed that past skills were insignificant for finding work in the Swedish job market.

Lack of specific national abilities categorizes skilled foreigners among the 'less talented laborers' regardless of their educational status. The information gathered portrayed the significance of past work experience in efforts to analyze the outcomes concerning Swedish degree significance in securing fruitful work. Majority 55% of the respondents agreed that specific work experience was critical in securing employment as opposed to 30% who differed with the hypothesis. The information they displayed shows past work and educational backgrounds were significant in setting a foothold in the Swedish labor market. These outcomes imply that prior knowledge and skills are important and can impact work as equally as nation's specific training.

Four respondents seeking entry into Swedish banking industry, based on their previous work experiences in their respective countries, were unable to secure employment in the first three years of their stay in the country only and only did after gaining Swedish work experience. One worked as low level salesman to gain this experience. Another one unsuccessfully applied for jobs without efforts to acquire this kind of experience. This case study paints a clear picture on the relationship between employability and Swedish work experience among high skilled immigrants.

In efforts to establish whether foreigners have equal employability chances in Sweden, results showed that foreigners who have both Swedish degrees and work experience did not have similar employability chances as those without one or both. Sixty-seven percent of the participants did not agree with the hypothesis that immigrants without Swedish work education and experience had the same employment chances as those with one or both requirements. Only 23% agreed with the hypothesis. These results imply that immigrants with Swedish work experience and expertise have higher chances of getting employment in Sweden in comparison with those without one or both. Two of the respondents agreed with the statement arguing that employers considered personal traits and past experiences without regard to the country of origin of an employee. Another respondent contradicted this equal employment opportunity between immigrants and native Swedes and argued that accessing work permits is not fair since for immigrants take more time.

Discrimination and prejudice

These were also considered one of the biggest impediments to employment among immigrants. Sixty-six percent participants considered these impeding factors while only 16.7% encountered segregation and biases in their employment-seeking processes. Significant amount of outcomes were collected on Swedish business inclination on Swedish work experiences which were employment hindrances affecting employment opportunities in the Swedish job market. This brings about the conclusion that employers in the Swedish labor market prefer employees with Swedish workplace experience and discriminate against those with similar qualifications and experiences from other countries. This amounts to prejudice and discrimination. 66.4% of the respondents believed that employers are inclined towards employees with Swedish workplace experiences is a form of discrimination and prejudice and has been a hindrance for immigrant workers with credentials in securing employment that match their skills and education. Only

15% of the respondents believed that this hypothesis was insignificant and the job search and recruitment processes. Efforts to examine discrimination of foreigners established inequality is seeking employment in Sweden.

One of the interviewed female respondents recounted being left out during a job recruitment drive in a top Swedish company. Being an engineer of foreign decent, she was left out despite having a wide range of experience in the engineering sector with a Master's degree in Project Management. She and another immigrant were they only ones left out while the rest of the 14 applicants shortlisted got absorbed. According to her, all the selected applicants of native decent only had bachelor's degree. This is a clear indication of widespread discrimination and prejudice in the Swedish job market.

Language proficiency

Language incompetence was cited by the respondents as one of the major obstacles to immigrant employment regardless of their education and professional skills. More than 50% of the respondents consider dialect a hindrance. 54.6% respondents that lack of language competence is a critical aspect in securing top employment positions in Sweden. The gathered information from efforts to approach Norwegian Swedish immigrants' employment obstacles displays similar outcomes. Respondents responded that Norwegians seeking employment in Sweden face challenges due to language proficiency reasons.

Most of the respondents lacked proficiency in the Swedish language but excellent communication skills and still cited language incompetency as a hindrance to meaningful employment seeking efforts (Kahaneck 2013). One respondent reported applying for over twenty jobs and being shortlisted in most of them but got turned down on the basis of her local language incompetence especially in writing. According to her, spoken and written Swedish language is a vital employment requirement in most Swedish organizations for communication and good

customer relation purposes. She adds that she as a result pursuing local language training in order to boost her employment chances.

Results from this study indicate that immigrants still miss out on employment opportunities in spite of possessing high educational and professional skills as opposed to the case of native job seekers. In Sweden, more than 80% of non-European immigrants are classified as low skilled or unskilled (Castles, De Haas & Miller 2013). This classification portends that even high skilled immigrants are profiled as having insufficient skills and this makes it hard to identify and recognize individual potentials and therefore their contribution to national development (Koskella, 2013). The widespread perception that non Swedish degrees inferior to those offered in Swedish institutions is another hindrance to identification and recognition of individual potential and national contributions. This has resulted in Swedish workplace experience as being the biggest determining factor for employment. Immigrants lacking it end up in low paying jobs with poor conditions of work as most organizations do not recognize personal attributes, work ethics and attitudes to work.

The government of Sweden plays crucial roles in reducing unemployment levels among immigrants as it invests in employment mentoring programs. Long-term traineeships have also been employed by the Swedish government to empower skilled immigrants to start their own business initiatives or join companies (Grundsten 2015). This is a very important method of ensuring empowerment and increasing their income levels. Sweden being among nations that receive and host high number of immigrants and refugees from European nations has a program to move refugees out of concentration camps and social support systems for enrollment into work integration programs to help them set foothold in the new foreign environment. Such programs are very important in assessing and utilizing immigrants' educational qualifications,

work experiences, employment history and soft skills and would make sure they do not undergo tedious and unfair processes when looking for meaningful employment. Another program by the public employment service works to secure employment for immigrants and refugees with high professional skills helps obliterate impediments that immigrants face when looking for employment opportunities (Grundsten 2015). Some programs provide preparatory training courses and subsidies to work experiences and are therefore very important in developing and gaining Swedish skills, knowledge and experience.

Chapter Summary

This chapter used figures to analyze findings of the study and is fortified by explanations, results implications and inferences. This chapter, in addition, represents the hindrance appropriation and impacts on job finding processes in Sweden among high skilled immigrants. Language incompetency and employer preference for Swedish degrees and experiences are covered and presented as the biggest impediments to skilled immigrant employment. Language capability is presented as among the biggest impediments to skilled immigrant employment. Prejudice and segregation are also looked into and identified as a considerable concern to immigrants seeking employment opportunities. Four issues were found to be the biggest immigrant employment concern in Sweden, namely, Swedish language incompetence, Swedish education and experience preference and biases, segregation and prejudice. These though varied from one participant to the other as affecting their job application outcomes in high skilled job recruitment processes and in efforts to seek Swedish work experience.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSIN AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the study project and presents recommendations for future research directions on the poor high-skilled immigrant absorption in Sweden. The problem

statement and research questions revealed that the main obstacles to immigrants' full entry into the Swedish job market were lack of Swedish workplace experience, lingual incompetence and non-recognition of overseas credentials, education, qualifications, work experience and employment. This study collected the views of 130 participants from diverse professions, ages and countries with assumptions that this sample fairly represented the views of all foreigners in Sweden who are in the process of seeking employment in the Swedish labor market.

The study also found that immigrants from diverse origins are entering Sweden and hence needed time for adjustment and adaptation to the Swedish social and economic environments as well as climatic and weather patterns and this was also found to be a determinant in securing employment since immigrant employees who have not adjusted to the new conditions and might in that case prefer employing native Swedes (Lillie, Caro, Bernstsen and Wagner 2013). Another observation was the fact that not all immigrants held formal employment positions in the Swedish job market. In fact, most of them entered the Swedish job market from low levels and rose in time to desired positions. The Swedish job market was a big attraction to immigrants supplying much labor. Increased immigrant employee number in the Swedish labor market would lead to a decrease in demand of their services as per the law of demand and supply (Corluy & Verbist 2014). This law explains why many immigrants remained unemployed in response to high influx of immigrants into the labor market leading to a decrease in demand of their services.

Open-ended interviews enabled asking of questions about experiences in their job search efforts in the Swedish job market and the obstacles encountered in the process that impeded their efforts (Jaumotte, Koloskova & Saxena 2016). A large number of participants cited linguistic incompetence as the biggest impediment to access to employment. Majority number of

respondents portends that they still put Swedish language behind their native languages and this fact affected their employability in significant magnitudes. In addition, non-recognition of overseas qualifications was cited as a great impediment to securing work and noted that workers in non-regulated professions had increased chances if securing employment in the Swedish labor market in a shorter time span. Those that face discriminations also encounter challenges such as low wages despite awareness creation efforts and globalization taking effect in other parts of the world for years. It is also concerning that some parts of the world with high economic abilities and high exposure levels as Swedish community still struggling with discrimination against a section of its population (Irastorza & Bevelander 2014). Countries all over the world are working to confront inequality among different races and social classes and it is imperative that Sweden steps up its efforts in these areas.

Sweden should be an embodiment of equality and free society with equal opportunities to all devoid of discrimination based on races, nature and ethnic backgrounds in its efforts to attaining the Swedish dream (Bosetti, Cattaneo & Verdolini 2015). The citizens of Sweden should abandon their discriminative, materialistic and selfish ways for the sake of national growth. Swedes should work to ensure they have educational opportunities, improved healthcare and job training by working together and changing the national principles to meet its challenges (Birgier, Lundh, Haberfeld & Ellder 2016).

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